

MECHANICAL MODEL OF 3-DIMENSIONAL MULTI-STEP BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The mechanical model of 8-step braided composites has been proposed for more comprehensive understanding of three-dimensional (3-D) textile composites. The analysis includes the geometric model of unit cells, microstructural characteristics (i.e., yarn orientation and fiber volume fraction), and prediction of elastic constants of the composites. The coordinate transformation and the averaging of stiffness and compliance constants are utilized in the prediction of elastic constants. Since nine types of unit cells are identified in the thickness and width directions of 8-step braided composites, characterization of mechanical properties is based upon the macro-cell, which occupies the entire cross-section and the unit pitch length of the sample. Relatively good correlation has been observed between the model prediction and the test results of the carbon/epoxy composite samples.

KEYWORDS: 8-step braiding, unit cell, coordinate transformation, macro-cell, average stiffness, compliance, elastic constants

INTRODUCTION

Recent development of textile preforming technology has significantly expanded the potential of three-dimensional (3-D) textile composites in various applications. Among several types of 3-D reinforcements the braided preforms have gained considerable attention due to the possibility of near-net shaping [1,2]. However, the application of 3-D rectangular braided composites has some limitations due to the slow fabrication speed and cross-sectional size. There have been a lot of efforts to overcome the limitation of 3-D braiding. An automated 2-step braiding machine has been developed to increase the preforming speed [3], and the concept of multi-step braiding has been proposed to broaden the range of attainable braid architecture [4]. Kostar and Chou [4] has demonstrated that the multi-step braiding can produce 2-step, 4-step and 8-step braids.

By utilizing the concept of the multi-step braiding, the possibility of the microstructural design of 3-D braided composites can be enlarged. The 2-step and 4-step braids have been the subjects of extensive studies [5-8] due to their unique microstructure and performance characteristics. Although axial yarns can be inserted into a 4-step braid, the amount of axial yarn volume is less than that could be achieved in 2-step braids. Thus, the longitudinal elastic stiffness of 4-step braided composites is lower than that of 2-step braided composites but, 4-step braids are more conformable to a curved shape. The geometric pattern of 8-step braids is close to that of 4-step braids, resulting in the similar characteristics for the composites performance. The advantage of 8-step braid is that the structure is more integrated than the 4-

step when the braider yarn angle is very small. This is due to the fact that the machine cycle of the 8-step braiding doubles that of the 4-step braiding, and the braider yarns are intertwined at a longer pitch length. Although Kostar and Chou [4] suggested that the 8-step braids can be applied to hybrid composites where specific fibers can be placed in the desired location, there seems to be size limitation for this effect.

The development of three-dimensionally reinforced materials are associated not only with the manufacturing processes of textile preforms and composites but also with the assessment of structural performance of the composites. Considerable effort has been made by researchers to evaluate the effectiveness of various 3-D textile composites [9]. Most of the previous studies on the analytic characterization of 3-D textile composites have shown that the proposed unit cells do not represent the entire structure of braided composites. Recently, Byun and Chou [5] have proposed a macro-cell model which describes accurate representation of 3-D braided composites. In an attempt to extend the applicability of the analytic methodology into other types of braided composites, the mechanical model is developed in this paper to predict the elastic constants of 8-step braided composites, and the correlation between the model prediction and the experimental results is made. The analysis includes identifying the unit cell structures and macro-cell approach based upon the averaging technique.

8-STEP BRAIDING PROCESS

The 8-step braiding [4], which is an extension of the 4-step braiding, involves shifting distance of column movement is twice as that of rows as depicted schematically in Fig. 1. The yarn arrangement is $[8 \times 4]$ in the figure, where the numbers of column and row carriers of the machine bed are 8 and 4, respectively. It is noted that at the end of eight steps (i.e., one machine cycle) the

Fig. 1: 8-step braiding process [4]

yarn carrier arrangement is the same as the initial configuration, although the individual carriers have changed their locations. In the 3-D braiding process, the arrangement of braiding yarns determines the number of axial yarns and the cross-sectional shape of the braid. The preform is advanced by the given pitch length after specified steps, and this sequence repeats to produce a desired preform length.

The key geometric parameters are the pitch length and the braider yarn angle. The pitch length is the take-up distance of the preform, and the braider yarn angle is the lower angle between the axial direction of the preform and braiding yarns. The surface of an 8-step braided preform is shown in Fig. 2. The pattern is characterized by the braider yarn angle, θ , and the pitch length, h . Although the braider yarn angle is the most important parameter in designing the preform, it is not easy to control the angle directly. Since the pitch length and the braider yarn angle has a reciprocal relation [5], the pitch length is usually controlled in the braiding process.

Fig.2: The surface of an 8-step braided preform

GEOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS

Unit Cells

Identification

The identification of unit cells is to determine the orientation angle of the braider yarn. If the yarn movement is independent of one another and there are no interactions among them, unit cells can be easily identified from the braider yarns on the machine bed. In the real situation, however, yarns shift the locations due to the cross-over pass with each other, and their cross-sectional shapes are deformed. Those changes also occur in accordance with mold size, which determines the dimension of the composite specimen. The accurate description of the microstructure can be achieved by observing the yarn cross-sections cut from the progressive sections of a composite specimen along the longitudinal direction. This procedure has been successfully applied to the unit cell identification of 4-step braided composites [5]. Due to the machine operation in Fig.1, the yarn arrangement in the cross-section of the composite is 180° rotated configuration with respect to the central point of the section. After the cross-section was photographed, the specimen was sanded to remove a thin layer of Δt , and the surface is polished again for observation. By plotting each yarn at every successive cut, the

yarn path was constructed as shown in Fig. 3. It should be noted that only the representative yarn paths were plotted for clarity, and the distance between two neighboring point is Δt in the longitudinal direction (x-axis).

Fig. 3: Yarn path of an 8-step braided composites for [8x4] arrangement

Idealization

Based upon Fig. 3, the unit cells of the composite can be constructed. Nine different types of unit cells can be identified as shown in Fig. 4. Each unit cell is idealized as a parallelepiped containing a single yarn. The unit cell geometry can be described by the yarn orientation angle, and the unit cell size (h, a, and b). Here, h is the pitch length, and a and b are related to the yarn movement on the machine bed and the preform compaction in the mold. Parameters a and b can be obtained from the width and the thickness of the sample. It is noted that the yarn at the sides of the sample occupies half of the yarn width.

$$a = \frac{W}{m+1} \quad ; \quad b = \frac{T}{n+2} \tag{1}$$

Utilizing Eqn 1, the braider yarn orientation angle can be expressed as follows:

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{h} \sqrt{a^2+b^2} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{h} \sqrt{a^2+4b^2} \right) \tag{2}$$

$$\theta_3 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2}{h} \sqrt{(2a)^2+b^2} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_4 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2a}{h} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_5 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2}{h} \sqrt{a^2+b^2} \right) \tag{3}$$

$$\theta_{6A} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{3}{h} \sqrt{a^2+b^2} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_{6B} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{3}{2h} \sqrt{a^2+4b^2} \right) \tag{4}$$

$$\theta_{7A} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{a}{h} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_{7B} = \theta_2 \tag{5}$$

$$\theta_{8A} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{3}{h} \sqrt{a^2+(b/2)^2} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_{8B} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{3}{2h} \sqrt{a^2+b^2} \right) \tag{6}$$

$$\theta_9 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{3}{h} \sqrt{(2a)^2+(3b)^2} \right) \tag{7}$$

Fiber Volume Fraction and Braider Yarn Angle

In order to analyze the macroscopic characteristics of 3-D textile composites, it is necessary to employ the *macro-cell* approach. This approach is effective in characterizing the complex structure of 3-D textile composites, in which no single unit cell repeats in the thickness and width directions. For the case of 8-step braided composites, the macro-cell encompasses the entire cross-section and the unit pitch length. Since the yarn cross-sectional area and the orientation angle have been obtained in the previous sections, the yarn volume in the macro-cell can be readily determined by multiplying the yarn area with the actual yarn length :

$$V_i = \frac{\lambda h}{\rho \kappa \cos \theta_i} \quad (i = 1 - 9) \quad (8)$$

where, λ , ρ and κ are the linear density of the yarn (kg/m), fiber density (kg/m³) and fiber packing fraction. The fiber packing fraction is the local fiber volume fraction of the yarn. Thus, the fiber volume fraction of the 8-step braided composite can be determined by considering the number of each unit cell and the fiber packing fraction.

$$V_f = \frac{\kappa \sum N_p V_p}{WTh} \quad (9)$$

where, N_p is the number of unit cell type p in the macro-cell as shown in Fig. 5. Similarly, the braider yarn orientation angle (θ_a) can be obtained by averaging the yarn angle for each unit cell and by taking into account the number of unit cells in the macro-cell.

$$\theta_a = \frac{\sum N_p \theta_p}{m(n+2)+n} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 4: Unit cells for 8-step braided composites

	1	2	6	2	6	2	6	2	
3	4	3	4	3	4	9	7	9	
	9	8	5	6	5	3	5	3	5
5	3	5	3	5	6	5	8	9	
	9	7	9	4	3	4	3	4	3
	2	6	2	6	2	6	2	1	

Fig. 5: Unit cell distribution in the macro-cell

COMPOSITE ELASTIC PROPERTIES

The elastic properties of 8-step braided composites can be predicted based upon the fiber and matrix properties and the three-dimensional fiber architecture. From the unit cell identification, the macro-cell of the braided composites can be regarded as an assemblage of anisotropic elastic unit cells whose properties are those of spatially oriented yarn and the matrix system. Since the principal material direction of the three-dimensionally located yarn do not coincide with the coordinate directions of our interest, the stress-strain relations are transformed from one coordinate system to another. Then, the effective elastic constants of 3-D textile composites can be obtained in two ways, either by assuming uniform stress or uniform strain throughout the macro-cell. The assumption of uniform stress implies a serial stacking of unit cells and averaging of compliance constants. In a similar manner, the case of uniform strain can be conceived as parallel arrangement of unit cells and averaging of stiffness constants.

Coordinate Transformation

Figure 6 shows the coordinate systems of a spatially oriented yarn segment. The local coordinate system is indicated as 1-2-3, where axis 1 coincides with axial yarn direction. In the global coordinate system, x-axis is along the composite longitudinal direction, and y-z-axes are in the width and thickness directions of the composite. The braider yarn orientation is indicated as θ , and angles, ϕ and ψ are defined as the *off-axis* and *inclination* angles, respectively.

Fig. 6: Coordinate systems of a spatially oriented yarn segment

The compliance matrix of the composite cylinder in the 1-2-3 coordinate system is expressed as follows due to the transverse isotropy,

$$[S] = \begin{pmatrix} 1/E_{11} & -\nu_{21}/E_{22} & -\nu_{21}/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & 1/E_{22} & -\nu_{32}/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_{11} & -\nu_{23}/E_{22} & 1/E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where the Young's modulus E_{ij} , shear modulus G_{ij} , and Poisson's ratio ν_{ij} are obtained from the fiber and matrix properties using micro-mechanics analysis. Then, the compliance matrix of the unidirectional composite rod, referring to the 123 coordinate system, is transformed to $[S']$, referring to the xyz coordinate system:

$$[S'] = [T]^t [S] [T] \quad (12)$$

where $[T]$ is the transformation matrix, and $[T]^t$ is a transposed matrix of $[T]$. The general transformation matrix between the local and the global coordinate systems has the following form [10]:

$$[T] = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1^2 & \alpha_2^2 & \alpha_3^2 & 2\alpha_2\alpha_3 & 2\alpha_3\alpha_1 & 2\alpha_1\alpha_2 \\ \beta_1^2 & \beta_2^2 & \beta_3^2 & 2\beta_2\beta_3 & 2\beta_3\beta_1 & 2\beta_1\beta_2 \\ \gamma_1^2 & \gamma_2^2 & \gamma_3^2 & 2\gamma_2\gamma_3 & 2\gamma_3\gamma_1 & 2\gamma_1\gamma_2 \\ \beta_1\gamma_1 & \beta_2\gamma_2 & \beta_3\gamma_3 & \beta_2\gamma_3 + \beta_3\gamma_2 & \beta_1\gamma_3 + \beta_3\gamma_1 & \beta_1\gamma_2 + \beta_2\gamma_1 \\ \gamma_1\alpha_1 & \gamma_2\alpha_2 & \gamma_3\alpha_3 & \gamma_2\alpha_3 + \gamma_3\alpha_2 & \gamma_1\alpha_3 + \gamma_3\alpha_1 & \gamma_1\alpha_2 + \gamma_2\alpha_1 \\ \alpha_1\beta_1 & \alpha_2\beta_2 & \alpha_3\beta_3 & \alpha_2\beta_3 + \alpha_3\beta_2 & \alpha_1\beta_3 + \alpha_3\beta_1 & \alpha_1\beta_2 + \alpha_2\beta_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where α, β , and γ with subscripts are direction cosines, which can be simplified by setting the 2-axis perpendicular to the z-axis from Fig. 6 :

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \cos(1,x) = \cos\phi \cos\psi ; & \alpha_2 &= \cos(1,y) = \sin\phi \cos\psi ; & \alpha_3 &= \cos(1,z) = \sin\psi \\ \beta_1 &= \cos(2,x) = -\sin\phi ; & \beta_2 &= \cos(2,y) = \cos\phi ; & \beta_3 &= \cos(2,z) = 0 \\ \gamma_1 &= \cos(3,x) = -\cos\phi \sin\psi ; & \gamma_2 &= \cos(3,y) = -\sin\phi \sin\psi ; & \gamma_3 &= \cos(3,z) = \cos\psi \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The coordinate transformation is conducted for the yarn segment in the unit cells. From Fig. 4, ϕ and ψ for each unit cell can be expressed as follows.

$$\phi_i = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\tan\theta_i}{\sqrt{1+R_i^2}} \right] ; \quad \psi_i = \tan^{-1} (R_i \sin\phi_i) \quad (i = 1 - 9) \quad (15)$$

where, R is the length ratio of the yarn segment in the y-direction with respect to that in the z-direction. For example, $R_1 = b/a$, $R_3 = b/2a$, $R_4 = 0$, $R_{6a} = b/a$, and $R_{6b} = 2b/a$. By combining Eqns 14 and 15, transformation matrix $[T]$ can be calculated for each type of unit cell, and the transformed compliance constants of braider yarns in the global coordinate system are determined from Eqn 12.

Elastic Constants

Considering the macro-cell (Fig. 5) under external force in the x-direction, the uniform strain can be assumed for each unit cell. For the yarns in the unit cell {8}, however, their various reinforcing directions result different elastic constants. Unit cell {8} consists of three yarn segments which are arranged in series with respect to the x-axis. Thus, the uniform stress assumption is applied for these yarn segments, and the transformed compliance constants of these segments are averaged based upon their projected length in the x-axis. The other types of unit cells do not need this averaging process because the yarn segments are in parallel arrangement in those unit cells. The averaged compliance constants of unit cell {8} is :

$$(S'_{ij})_8 = \frac{1}{3} (S'_{ij})_{8a} + \frac{2}{3} (S'_{ij})_{8b} \quad (16)$$

where, S'_{ij} is the transformed compliance constants of each yarn segment.

In the macro-cell, in which all the unit cells are arranged in parallel under the loading in the x-direction, the deformation properties of the composite is obtained by averaging the stiffness constants of unit cells based upon their volume contribution.

$$C_{ij}^c = \frac{\sum N_p V_p (C'_{ij})_p}{W_{Th}} + (1 - \frac{\sum N_p V_p}{W_{Th}}) (C_{ij})_m \quad (p = 1 - 9) \quad (17)$$

where, V and C'_{ij} with subscript, p , refer to the yarn volume and inverted stiffness matrix from S'_{ij} of each type of unit cell . The subscript m denotes the matrix material. It should be noted that the yarn volume is considered in Eqn 17 because the stiffness and compliance matrices are for the unidirectional composites. Finally, the stiffness matrix of the macro-cell is inverted to the compliance matrix, S_{ij}^c , and the elastic constants are then obtained as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} E_{xx} &= 1/S_{11}^c \quad ; \quad E_{yy} = 1/S_{22}^c \quad ; \quad E_{zz} = 1/S_{33}^c \\ G_{yz} &= 1/S_{44}^c \quad ; \quad G_{zx} = 1/S_{55}^c \quad ; \quad G_{xy} = 1/S_{66}^c \\ \nu_{xy} &= - S_{12}^c / S_{11}^c \quad ; \quad \nu_{zx} = - S_{31}^c / S_{11}^c \quad ; \quad \nu_{yz} = - S_{32}^c / S_{22}^c \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

CORRELATION

The 8-step braids were fabricated using 12K T300 carbon fiber, and the consolidation of the preforms was accomplished by the resin transfer molding (RTM) technique using the epoxy and curing agent. The samples were cured at 150 °C for two hours. In order to verify the analytical characterization of 8-step braided composites, experiments on mechanical response have been conducted. Tensile test was performed to measure the longitudinal modulus and Poisson's ratio of the composites. The dimension of specimens was 12.9 mm x 4.3 mm x 229 mm, and they were instrumented with biaxial strain gages of 6.35 mm in gage length. All tests were conducted on a screw-driven Instron machine at a cross-head speed of 1.27 mm/min.

Table 1 summarizes the input data for the calculation, and the results of model prediction and experiments. Relatively good correlation between the model prediction and the test results can be observed. It is also noted that three-dimensional elastic constants can be predicted in the proposed mechanical model. This can provide important data in analyzing and designing the structures consisting of 3-D textile composites.

Table 1: Input data for calculation, the model predictions and experimental results

Input Data		Model Prediction	Test Results
<i>Mechanical Data</i>	<i>Geometric and Physical Data</i>	<i>Engineering Constants</i>	<i>Engineering Constants</i>
T300 Carbon Fiber	T = 4.3 mm	$E_{xx} = 62.7$ GPa	$E_{xx} = 65.1$ GPa
$E_{1f} = 240$ GPa	W = 12.9 mm	$E_{yy} = 9.97$ GPa	$E_{yy} = -$
$E_{2f} = 16.6$ GPa	h = 15.0 mm	$E_{zz} = 10.38$ GPa	$E_{zz} = -$
$G_{12f} = 8.27$ GPa	[m x n] = [8 x 4]	$G_{yz} = 3.77$ GPa	$G_{yz} = -$
$G_{23f} = 5.89$ GPa	$\kappa = 0.8$	$G_{zx} = 4.70$ GPa	$G_{zx} = -$
$\nu_{12f} = 0.26$	$\lambda = 8.212 \times 10^{-4}$ (kg/m)	$G_{xy} = 5.06$ GPa	$G_{xy} = -$
Epoxy	$\rho = 1.77 \times 10^3$ (kg/m ³)	$\nu_{yz} = 0.34$	$\nu_{yz} = -$
$E_m = 4$ GPa		$\nu_{zx} = 0.25$	$\nu_{zx} = -$
$\nu_m = 0.38$		$\nu_{xy} = 0.35$	$\nu_{xy} = 0.37$
		<i>Geometric Characteristics</i>	<i>Geometric Characteristics</i>
		$\theta = 12^\circ$	$\theta = 14^\circ$
		$V_f = 0.46$	$V_f = 0.485$

CONCLUSION

- (1) A mechanical model has been proposed to predict the elastic properties of 8-step braided composites. Nine types of unit cell were identified by observing the sample cross-section in a progressive cut. The analytical approach for characterizing the 8-step braided composite was based upon the macro-cell, which basically occupies the entire cross-section and unit pitch length of the sample.
- (2) The coordinate transformation and the averaging of stiffness and compliance constants are utilized in the prediction of elastic constants. The experimental results compared favorably with the model predictions. Although the experimental characterization was not enough to support the model prediction due to the lack of established test methods for 3-D textile composites, the methodology introduced in this paper can be effectively utilized by the materials and structural designers in obtaining the three-dimensional elastic constants of the composites.

REFERENCES

1. Chou, T-W., *Microstructural Design of Fibrous Composites*, Chapter 6 & 7, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1992.
2. Chou, T-W. and Ko, F.K., *Textile Structural Composites*, Pipes, R.B., Editor, Elsevier Science Publisher, 1989.
3. Byun, J-H., "Development of an Automated 2-Step Braiding Machine and the Process Model", *Proceedings of Innovative Processing and Characterization of Composite Materials*, ASME WAM, 1995, pp. 305-315.
4. Kostar, T.D. and Chou, T-W., "Process Simulation and Fabrication of Advanced Multi-Step Three-Dimensional Braided Preforms", *J. Mat. Sci.*, 1994, Vol. 29, p. 2159.
5. Byun, J-H. and Chou, T-W., "Process-microstructure relationship of 2-step and 4-step braided composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, 1996, Vol. 56, pp. 235-251.
6. Pandya, R. and Hahn, H.T., "Designing with 4-Step Braided Fabric Composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, 1996, Vol. 56, pp. 623-634.
7. Du, G-W, Popper, P., and Chou, T-W.1991. "Analysis of 3-D Textile Preforms for Multi-directional Reinforcement of Composites", *J. Mat. Sci.*, Vol. 26, pp.3438-3448.
8. Macander, A.B., Crane, R.M., and Camponeschi, E.T., "Fabrication and Mechanical Properties of Multidimensionally (X-D) Braided Composite Materials", ASTM STP 873, 1986, pp. 422-445.
9. Byun, J-H., and Chou, T-W., "Three-Dimensional Textile Composites: A Review", 112th ASME Winter Annual Meeting, *Symposium on Composites in Transportation Vehicles*, Atlanta, Georgia, Dec.1-6, 1991.
10. Lekhnitskii, S.G., *Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Elastic Body*, San Francisco, Holden-Day, 1963.